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INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY: A VEHICLE OF TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER

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ABSTRACT

Information technology is an indispensable tool for economic and industrial survival. This paper identifies some of the areas where information is capable of assisting the country in technology transfer. Suggestions were equally provided on how information technology can be improved upon.

INTRODUCTION

Information technology is a modern technique and innovative approach to information acquisition, storage and dissemination of processed data to end users through electronic media. Information technology is so vital that the survival of a nation depends to induce expected change in the world of works to be relevant especially in modern times. As relevant and important as the knowledge of information technology is to all categories of people, workers, government officials, businessmen and the students, quite a lot of Nigerians may still remain in the dark as far as its acquisition is.

Information technology is now a new order that is changing fast in all facets of human existence ranging from the economy, social life and politics as well as other sectors that are capable of re - engineering the Nigerian vision. It is against this development that ushers in a marriage of convenience of information and communication technologies have not only reduced long distance to a global village but have collapsed our systems to make it inter - operational.

With the advancement in information and communication technology, it is now becoming increasingly difficult for the more developed nations to ignore the unhealthy rate of information advancement in the developing ones if they are to maintain and sustain economic growth.

In recent development, information and communication technology (ICT) has led to global village and indeed a revolution as important as the industrial revolution which now dictates the pace in world development. Information Technology represents major opportunity for developing countries that can access and use efficiently and effectively as a threat to those who cannot. In order to achieve maximum benefit, government must evolve a well coordinated ICT programme which should be a national priority especially in this era of information explosion. Information technology cannot efficiently function without particular attention paid to infrastructural facilities such as electricity supply and reliable telecommunication as the main configuration of technology. In a country like ours, efforts should be geared towards effective stabilisation of tight and other factors that can make information technology a reality not a mystery.

One of the products of information technology is the rapid technological development and information revolution that is not only dynamic but very reliable for the country.

There is no doubt that information and dependable for promoting socio - economic growth technology is a vehicle of social transformation and technology transfer.

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This phenomenon will affect directly or indirectly the technology transfer that is capable of improving the quality of life and technological behaviours of our citizenry. It is against this background that information technology consciousness is unique especially in this era of information precision. In considering the marketability of many companies utilities, medical, banking and the likes, the availability of basic information becomes an inevitability.

In the same way, protocol ruled networked computers can be connected locally. All businesses in all spheres of human endeavours can be successfully carried out electronically and in a more secured manner across the globe through internet or cyber cafe. It is now relevant and possible for a country to purchase and export a car displayed in American show room through Internet connectivity which is part of technology transfer.

Apart from this, internet connectivity has improved lot of businesses and other economic advancement among countries, multi - nationals and individuals. A subs of E - commerce is the 'smart card' which allows customers to enjoy services at mercantile outlets without the risk and inconvenience associated with physical cash deposited by various fraudsters (419).

Information technology also contributes immensely to technology transfer especially in tele-Education and E - learning. The demand for fast and accurate information is the concern of our society generally today. This is very necessary because there is a

dear need to bridge the educational gap among various groups. It has also become very important at this period of information explosion to extend the frontiers of knowledge via research and information and communication technology which is playing an unprecedented role in the area of technology transfer. For instance, a computer can be connected to the global ocean of information. In addition, with the rapid development in video conferencing, it is now possible for lecturers in one continent to give lectures on - line and off - line to another in different locations. For example, on - line interaction via speed media makes it possible to shrink the world into manageable proportion to enable one or two ways communications without actually travelling to a common site.

Apart from the fact that ICT will provide the avenue for optimal utilisation of human resources in the educational and industrial sectors, it also eases the learning notably Universities, Polytechnics and other sharing of manpower among various institution of allied research institutes, In fact technology transfer has also become important in some specialised discipline as Medicine and Engineering through on - line by the world's specialists.

In like manner, Tele - Education is another viable area which ICT has made possible for localised laboratories to share globally through the internet connectivity. For example rather than to duplicate expensive research equipment, a single one can be shared among institutions by pre - determined sensors and computers localised in these institutions connected via internet to the laboratory hosting the equipment or apparatus.

Similarly, Tele - Medicine and health are vital considering the delicacy of the job and the expectations areas through which technology transfer is inevitable of our society.

In fact, many of our specialists have gone to some advanced countries in seeking for green pastures and as such the expertise is lost to them where they are seriously needed. In the same vein, similar experiences are observed during manpower shifts from Saudi Arabia. Essentially technology transfer or drift information technology which will not only reduce the could be minimized with the effective use of cost implication, but set the right calibre of manpower and information precision. In fact the question of rural drift does not make any meaning, if ICE's improved and personnel or experts are trained to perform effective job. However rural health care can be provided through tele-diagnosis, tele-prescription as information and counselling well as tele-treatment. Dissemination of appropriate on public health and hygiene can be effected by the reliance on point - to video conferencing between media experts in cities point , point to multi-point, large band with wireless, and rural settings thereby improving quality and expectancy of life in more meaningful and fashionable ways.

Finally, information technology will not only capable of self - sustenance through improvement in agricultural productivity but will also lead to the establishment of community - based centres to educate our teeming population to re - orientate our thoughts towards a positive direction as a nation.

CONCLUSION

Information technology is an essential ingredient of technology transfer and the only way to reduce brain drain is to improve the information technology in order to meet the expectations of this generation whose consciousness and aspirations can only be satisfied through information technology's transfer.

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